

Processing and characterisation of Functionally Graded A356-10wt.%SiC_p Composite

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ABSTRACT

In this paper attempts were made to cast and synthesize functionally graded A356-10wt.%SiC_p composites with circular geometry using liquid stir casting technique followed by vertical centrifugal casting technique. An average particle size of 40 μm was used as the size of SiC_p reinforcement. The microstructure of the composite was examined using Leica optical microscope. The microstructural analysis revealed an outward radial gradient distribution of SiC reinforcement forming different zones and gradation in the distribution of SiC_p particles along the radial direction of the cast disc due to the effect of centrifugal force. Micro hardness values were found to increase in the radial direction of SiC_p distribution.

Keywords:- Functionally graded composite, SiC reinforcement, Microstructure, Micro hardness